

The Nuclear Power Plant Environment Monitoring System through Mobile Units

Authors : P. Tanuska, A. Elias, P. Vazan, B. Zahradnikova

Abstract : This article describes the information system for measuring and evaluating the dose rate in the environment of nuclear power plants Mochovce and Bohunice in Slovakia. The article presents the results achieved in the implementation of the EU project-Research of monitoring and evaluation of non-standard conditions in the area of nuclear power plants. The objectives included improving the system of acquisition, measuring and evaluating data with mobile and autonomous units applying new knowledge from research. The article provides basic and specific features of the system and compared to the previous version of the system, also new functions.

Keywords : information system, dose rate, mobile devices, nuclear power plant

Conference Title : ICCITE 2014 : International Conference on Communication and Information Technology and Engineering

Conference Location : Sydney, Australia

Conference Dates : December 15-16, 2014